

Constraints on the Presence of a Rocky Exoplanet Atmosphere from a JWST Transmission Spectrum

G. Fu, J. Lustig-Yaeger, E. M. May, K. N. Ortiz Ceballos, S. E. Moran, S. Peacock, K. B. Stevenson, M. López-Morales, R. J. MacDonald, L. C. Mayorga, D. K. Sing, K. S. Sothen, J. A. Valenti, J. Adams, M. K. Alam, N. E. Batalha, K. A. Bennett, J. Gonzalez-Quiles, J. Kirk, E. Kruse, J. D. Lothringer, Z. Rustamkulov, H.R. Wakeford
Too many affiliations to list

Abstract & Context

The critical first step in the search for life on exoplanets over the next decade is to determine whether rocky planets transiting small M-dwarf stars possess atmospheres (Seager et al. 2009; Mansfield et al. 2019) and, if so, what processes sculpt them over time (Segura et al. 2005; Tian et al. 2015; Luger et al. 2015). Because of its broad wavelength coverage and improved resolution compared to previous methods, spectroscopy with JWST offers a new capability to detect and characterize the atmospheres of Earth-sized, M-dwarf planets (Morley et al. 2017; Batalha et al. 2018).

Here we use JWST to independently validate the discovery of LHS 475b, a warm (586 K), 0.99 Earth-radius exoplanet, interior to the habitable zone, and report a precise 2.9 – 5.3 μm transmission spectrum. With two transit observations, we rule out primordial hydrogen-dominated and cloudless pure methane atmospheres. Thus far, the featureless transmission spectrum remains consistent with a planet that has a high-altitude cloud deck (similar to Venus), a tenuous atmosphere (similar to Mars), or no appreciable atmosphere at all (akin to Mercury). There are no signs of stellar contamination due to spots or faculae.

Our observations demonstrate that JWST has the requisite sensitivity to constrain the secondary atmospheres of terrestrial exoplanets with absorption features <50 ppm, and that our current atmospheric constraints speak to the nature of the planet itself, rather than instrumental limits.

The Target: LHS 475b

We observed two transits of LHS 475b (previously the planet candidate TOI 910.01) on 31 August 2022 and 4 September 2022 with JWST's Near InfraRed Spectrograph (NIRSpec) G395H instrument mode as part of the JWST Cycle 1 Guest Observing (GO) Program 1981 (PI: K. Stevenson).

This mode covers wavelengths 2.87-5.27 μm and has a native spectral resolving power of $R \sim 2700$. We used the Bright Object Time Series (BOTS) mode with the NRSRAPID readout pattern, S1600A1 slit, and the SUB2048 subarray. Each time-series observation lasted a total of 2.9 hours, which captured the 39.98 ± 4.04 minute transit that occurred during this window. This resulted in approximately 1.75 hours and 0.5 hours of stellar baseline before and after transit, respectively.

We selected the LHS 475 system as one of several nearby M-dwarf systems with known or candidate rocky planets. Prior to validation, LHS 475b was classified as a planet candidate first identified in Sector 12 by the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS; Ricker et al. 2015). TESS observed subsequent transits of the planet in Sectors 13, 27, and 39. LHS 475b transits a 3300 K, 0.2789 solar radius M3.5V dwarf star on a 2.029-day orbital period Stassun et al. (2019). This planet is likely to be tidally locked, with a permanent dayside facing its host star, and an equilibrium temperature of 586 K.

Transmission Spectrum of a Rocky Planet

The observed JWST transmission spectrum is featureless. A flat line, representative of an airless-body or high mean molecular weight (MMW) atmosphere, provides the best fit to the spectrum. Despite the featureless spectrum, the precision is sufficiently high to rule out several archetypal atmospheric compositions:

Figure 2 – The final, binned transmission spectrum (black points) compared to models (colored lines). The data are most consistent with a pure carbon dioxide atmosphere or that of an airless body.

Top: Our data strongly (>10 sigma) rule out hydrogen-dominated atmospheres with compositions from 1–100x solar metallicity, with reduced-chi-squared values reported in the legend for each model. The blue shaded bar highlights the region detailed in the bottom panel.

Bottom: Our data also rule out, though to lower significance (2 – 5 sigma), high mean molecular weight compositions of 1000x solar metallicity and a pure methane atmosphere. We weakly disfavor a pure water atmosphere and an Earth composition atmosphere. Each model is plotted relative to the mean transit depth.

If it's not airless, models favor a high MMW atmosphere that is either thin or cloudy

Figure 4 – Retrieval results showing preferred atmospheric properties for models containing H_2O , CO_2 , CH_4 , and CO , plus a variable bulk gas composition for LHS 475b given the transmission spectrum measurements. Darker color shading indicates higher relative posterior probability density as a function of the apparent surface pressure (P_0), molecular weight (μ) of the bulk atmospheric constituent (left), and isothermal scale height (H , right). Dashed contours denote the 1-sigma (white), 2-sigma (gray), and 3-sigma (black) Bayesian credible regions. The red arrow depicts how the Jeans escape flux depends on the scale height and emphasizes the region of the parameter space that is more susceptible to atmospheric escape. If the planet possesses an atmosphere with at least 1 ppm CO_2 or CH_4 , then the models prefer high mean molecular weight, compact atmospheres ($\mu > 20$ g/mol at 1.2-sigma; $H < 25$ km at 1.2-sigma) with low apparent surface pressures ($P_0 < 0.01$ bar at 1.3-sigma; $P_0 < 1$ bar at 2-sigma). These scenarios correspond to either a tenuous or cloudy secondary atmosphere.

We place a 3-sigma constraint on the maximum size of absorption features in our spectrum at 61 ppm for H_2O at 2.8 μm , 38 ppm for CH_4 at 3.3 μm , 49 ppm for CO_2 at 4.3 μm , and 62 ppm for CO at 4.6 μm . These constraints demonstrate JWST's sensitivity to absorption features smaller than 50 ppm for an Earth-sized exoplanet.

No evidence of an atmosphere does not imply evidence of no atmosphere. Further observations will be required to determine whether LHS 475b possesses an atmosphere.